

Metaphors in Media Discourse: A Closer Look at Newspapers

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Abstract: As newspapers follow editorial work, the author's identity remains in the background. Hence, newspapers' discursive features should be studied from textual perspectives to understand the social dimension of the messages produced in such texts. What is more, pragmatically, the text as a whole and its separate language units with their structural elements require careful attention. Thus, this paper aims to analyze onomastic metaphors as one of the structural-stylistic types functioning in the language of newspapers. We analyzed the Moskovskij Komsomolets, Arguments and Facts, Komsomolskaya Pravda, Rossiyskaya Gazeta, and Izvestia during our analysis, with specific attention paid to the proper names as the binding elements with their substantial and semantic functions. Our results suggest that certain metaphorical language uses appear repetitively in the texts.

Anahtar Sözcükler:

Özel isim,
onim,
eğretileme,
metafor,
media söylemi,
edimibilim

Medya Söyleminde Metaforlar: Gazetelere Yakınsak Bir Bakış

Özet: Gazeteler editoryal çalışmalarını takip ederken yazarın kimliği arka planda kalıyor. Dolayısıyla gazetelerin söylemsel özelliklerinin metinsel açıdan incelenmesi, bu tür metinlerde üretilen mesajların toplumsal boyutunun anlaşılması açısından önemlidir. Üstelik edimibilimsel olarak sadece metnin bütünü değil, aynı zamanda yapısal unsurlarıyla birlikte ayrı ayrı dil birimleri de dikkat gerektirir. Böylelikle bu makale, gazete dilinde işleyen yapısal-üslup türlerinden biri olan onomastik metaforları incelemeyi amaçlamaktadır. İncelememiz sırasında Moskovskij Komsomolets, Argümanlar ve Gerçekler, Komsomolskaya Pravda, Rossiyskaya Gazeta ve Izvestia'yı, maddi ve anlamsal işlevleriyle bağlayıcı unsur olarak özel isimlere özellikle dikkat ederek inceledik. Sonuçlarımız bazı metaforik dil kullanımlarının metinlerde tekrar tekrar yer aldığını göstermektedir.

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1. Introduction

The mass media discourse possesses a powerful and ramified system (press, radio, TV, the Internet), including texts of various genres, one of which is newspaper. Newspapers continuously search for estimated means of expression through various speech elements (Ninsiana *et al.*, 2022; van Vuuren, 2023). It is important to note that language use in the media is not individual but social in character (Kotelnikov, 2021; Kyrchanoff, 2021; Minnegalieva *et al.*, 2020; Panova *et al.*, 2020; Pogosyan, 2021a; Pogosyan, 2021b). The social importance of a word in the language of the newspaper is expressed from the point of view of the producer of the speech. However, as newspapers follow editorial work, the identity of the author remains in the background (Fauzan, 2018; Koepke *et al.*, 2019; Krylova *et al.*, 2020; Mingazova *et al.*, 2019; Moloj & Adegioriolu, 2023; Siphukhanyo & Olawale, 2024). Hence, newspapers' discursive features should be studied from textual perspectives to understand the social dimension of the messages produced in such texts (Demichev, 2021; Borovkova, 2021; Abulhanova *et al.*, 2019; Nureeva *et al.*, 2019a; Nureeva *et al.*, 2019b; Omodan, 2023).

Now, big attention is being paid to the pragmatic approach in the analysis of language units at various levels. It is especially true, in our opinion, concerning the language of newspapers as the pragmatical characteristic of the given texts is available (Chong & Tsubota, 2023). However, at the present stage of the development of linguistics, the science insufficiently investigates semantic-stylistic mechanisms of pragmatical influence of the onomastic units in the language of newspapers. It also defines the urgency of the theme chosen by us. Hence, this paper aims to analyze onomastic metaphors as one of the structural-stylistic types functioning in the language of newspapers. While doing that, a special emphasis is placed on the functioning of proper names with their pragmatic effects.

2. Methods

The language of modern Russian newspapers is at the center of the attention of linguists as it possesses vast opportunities and the strongest influence on other versions of a literary language and society as a whole. Special attention is given to semantic and stylistic changes in the language of modern newspapers, the structure of the newspaper text, and its pragmatical aspect (Dube *et al.*, 2023; Fazyljanova, 2006; Kalimullina *et al.*, 2021; Rozental, 1981). The features marked by scientists describing newspaper texts (social estimated, the communicative general importance, expression) are simultaneously a sphere of interest for pragmatists as linguistic direction.

Pragmatically, the text as a whole and its separate language units as structural elements require careful attention. Ratnikova (2003) argues that word meanings depend on various interconnected factors such as social and cultural, psychological, and intralinguistic; contradictions make meaning possible mainly because such contradictions find “the expression, in particular, in occasional functioning language units” (p. 5) among which the case of the proper names is of utmost importance. Functionally, proper names serve as the most effective means of attracting attention to the text of any spoken or written discourse with their semantic capacity and aesthetic value. Alefirenko (1998) argues that the use of onyms is noteworthy “as the complex integrated phenomenon in which all basic language properties are combined” (p. 40).

Hence, in this study, we analyzed the following periodicals (newspapers) that were published since 1995: *the Moskovskij Komsomolets*, *Arguments and Facts*, *Komsomolskaya Pravda*, *Rossiyskaya*

Gazeta, and *Izvestia*. During the data collection and analysis process, we considered how the proper names were used as multifunctional signs mainly because they are the binding elements with their substantial and semantic functions. Then, each case-based onim was taken as a temporal onomastic symbol that functions to reproduce images or messages in thinking and speech. The authors of the present paper studied the texts individually and then compared their findings to achieve unity in their results.

3. Results and Discussion

It is necessary to note that in the newspaper, text dominates metaphorical periphrasis and is publicistic over the basis. The formation of periphrases based on structural models already available in language testifies to the system character and efficiency of graphic-expressive means of Russian. Often, the metaphor is a semantic basis of a pronomination - the stylistic reception consisting of replacing a nominal name with the proper name. It is possible to allocate two preconditions for the similar use of onims. The first one is the establishment of biunique conformity in cognition. The second one is their semantic functions, which stand for verbal signs.

According to the functional typology onomastic lexicon in our work, the following appear as the major onomastic metaphors:

1. anthroponymic (with an auxiliary component - the antroponym of the real person): *Yesterday all Russia welcomed Russian Napoleon [K.T., on February 14 2018] - about the leader of LDPR V.V. Zhirinovskij;*
2. toponymic (with an auxiliary component - the toponym): *The governor of Russian Alaska again surprises everybody [K.T., on September 10 2018] - about activity of the governor of Chukotka;*
3. poetonymic (with an auxiliary component - poetonym, that is proper name of the character of an artwork or poetic toponymic): *Khlestakov is from Omsk [K.II., on February 5, 2017] - about the swindler who has cheated officials of regional city.*

Ratnikova also allocates the idiomatic metaphor (with an auxiliary component - ideonym, i.e. proper name having denote in intellectual, ideological, art sphere of human activity): *the plan of Barbarossa for the Belarus collective farms, "Eugeny Onegin" for Poles - about Mickiewicz's "Sir Tadeushe", etc. (Ratnikova, 2003, p. 101).*

The first precondition of non-standard speech use of onims in the language of the mass media expressing in semantic transformations is incorporated in their lexical background, which reflects the cultural semantics of carriers of proper names (Baturina *et al.*, 2019, p. 14). Semantic expansion of onims is possible in language practice as fragments of reality are grouped around individuals, topos, and events (Vorobjeva & Baturina, 2012, p. 165). Such objects are examined in cultural science as means of translation of cultural information, its communicative analogue, and its unequivocal referention by proper names. The last one becomes assistant to the given information at a language level: *Piotrowsky's name for a long time designates a certain sum of qualities: intelligence, erudition, decency. Not casually in this family, there was unique for a museum of scale of the Hermitage a phenomenon of a dynasty [K.T., on March 3, 2018].*

As the estimation of the object in society is fixed, another variant of its perception enters the cognition base of native speakers, and the associations caused by its individual name get the usual character. It predetermines an opportunity for language functioning of onyms outside of a straight line of referention – first of all, for the name of that clot of the cultural

environment in consciousness which corresponds to the given object and circumstances surrounding it. Compare semantics of the onomastic concepts in the text: *Maradona is Borches, Эвита with Пероном* (Evita with Peron), *a tango and gaucho. Maradona is Argentina, its history and destiny* [News, on October 20, 2020]. Besides the onym of the culturally important object in stabilising its semantic structure (a lexical background, connotative sems) it is naturally used for pseudo-identification of other objects that are already considered by us (real or hypothetical) or groups of similar objects.

The dynamics of moods in a society influence the maintenance of onomastic units. Compare how changes in a lexical background of antroponyms are reflected in its contextual, not referent, value by the example of compound antroponym *Alexander Matrosov* (or a family variant *Matrosov*). The objective part of the information at the center of the onomastic concept *Alexander Matrosov* remains constant, changes mention the axiological part. Initially in, the last one is dominated by the sema “heroism”: *With such an attitude to militarism, which Russia shows, it is difficult to expect that Alexander Matrosov will appear in the army* [Russian paper, on March 29, 2017]. In modern mass communication, given antroponym is used basically for the achievement of the stylistic effect of irony, thus are contextually focused on such new axiological sems as «absence of choice, the compelled character of a feat» (on association with protecting groups, which task was to provide a due level of heroism in the fight), «senselessness of a feat», it «model character» and at last «the ideological program of potential heroes and their acts»: *party - governmental matrosov* - about the new prime minister entering a post at the moment of an economic crisis [AaF, on February 8, 2020]. In some cases, it can develop an original enantiosemya that contrasts with the onomastic meanings of the same unit marked during the different periods of history or given to it carriers of different social ideals. So, in the maintenance of the concept *Lenin* a) the volume of individual concept has changed in part due to the promulgation of new historical facts; б) has essentially changed the axiological component of onym (the estimation was replaced from plus to minus) therefore the antroponymic sign *Lenin* began to connote attributes “terror”, “cruelty”, “crime” and to be used in a synonymic line with antroponym *Hitler*: *Milosevic’s destiny, is the ex-dictator with the 13-years experience, «is small Lenin» was named him in press* [Russian paper, on October 9 2019]; *If there is suddenly in a history Lenin, Stalin or Hitler, it means that the mass consciousness for its triumph has matured* [K.T., On November, 24, 2019].

The change that began in the post-Soviet epoch of orientations and ideals, dying off of social stereotypes, and audit of an official history has caused falling myths of some case persons and, accordingly, changes in the lexical background of their onyms and the maintenance of their symbols. For example, names connotating cosmopolitanism, slander, and absence of patriotism represented the most positive features and high estimations (*Solzhenitsin, Brodskiy*, etc.). On the other hand, revision of estimations of historical processes, exposure of falsifications of history or distortions of the facts and tendentious illumination of events in precedent works of art has led to the desacralization of corresponding antroponymic and poetonymic signs, such as *Lenin, Dzerzhinskij/iron Felics, Stalin, Pavlik Morozov, Oleg Koshevoy, Pavka Korchagin*, etc.

Becoming a precedent of a onym belongs entirely to the sphere of culture, which is outside only language phenomena. *Do you remember the old test? The answer, not reflecting: the poet - Pushkin, the river - Volga, the composer - Bax. And the composer of cinema - it is correct, Isaak Schwarz* [M.K., on September 4, 2019]. As the estimation of objects in society is fixed, another variant of its perception enters the cognition base of native speakers, and the associations caused by its individual name get the usual character (Abdullaev et al., 2021; Lyapun, 1999; Volina, 1994).

The second precondition of not referent using of onyms is deduced by us that verbal units available in the language system do not settle all opportunities of combination theory of elements of meaning. In the course of the cognition development of a changing reality, even before the generation of the corresponding text constantly arises new steady combinations of senses which, in the process of fastening in consciousness, aspire to lexicalize in language. The certificate that the person as an individual phenomenon was transformed into a precedent stereotype as an abstract, collective image can serve the use of antroponym in the form of plural. However, it is necessary to approach an estimation of this grammatic phenomenon with care as systematization forms of the plural of onyms, as is known, it is ambiguous. In some contexts, they really are certificates leaving of onomastic lexeme from the true carrier, its transformation into a self-valuable cultural and language phenomenon: *the Native land is not zhirinovstiyе, medvedevy, putiny* [News, on November 9, 2017].

Finally, one more language parameter of becoming an onym as a fact of culture is its occurrence in the precedent statement. It can be а) inclusion given onym in already existing precedent statement: *Chubays hazе covers the sky; If Chubays was not, it would be necessary to invent him* [News, on February 26, 2018]; б) formation of the new precedent statement on the basis of given onym: *Chubays is guilty for everything (many sources)*. Also, Bill Gates is their Chubays [News, on August 15, 2019], concerning the fact that it is accepted to abuse Bill Gates among programmers.

Precedention is a characteristic of the functioning of onomastic units in the newspaper text. In the headings of articles, authors frequently use various sorts of transformations which bear the pragmatical characteristic of concentrating attention on itself (Pogosyan, 2021). Within the framework of the text structure, each element of publicistic speech carries out the text-forming function. Proper names alongside with nominative (differential, identification) function carry out the text forming (onyms are the essential means of the text formation) (Voronova, 2000, p. 28). Under the text forming function proper names, we understand the ability of onym to be a binding, constructive element of substantial - semantic space and the formal organization of the publicistic text.

Our results suggest that the following models of metaphorical language uses appear to be widely used in newspapers:

1. Name - the character of the person: *the World got rid of Saddam Husejna - he is Stalin of the present, and what is farther?* [K.T., on August 6, 2017];
2. A name → a sort of activity, a profession: *Yelena Blavatskaya is Jul Vern of mysticism* [K.T., On August 16, 2017]; *As a matter of fact Pelevin is Ljev Tolstoy of the present* [K.T., on September 9, 2018];
3. A name → behaviour: *This huge Othello (about a vagrant dog - L.B.) ... gives nobody pass!* [M.K., on April, 17, 2018];
4. A name → primacy, order: *who will be Gagarin on Mars?* [Russian paper, on August 6, 2019].

On the other hand, the class “is frequently projected” for a certain name carrying, as a rule, one attribute. So, speaking *Mariya Ivanovna* in a certain context, the native speaker means the school’s teacher. If, in a context, there is the onym *Ivan*, as a rule, this onym carries a principal meaning - is an attribute of national identity - Russian (compare with the onym *Frits*, which at the same predominating attribute characterizes the German):

1. A trade → a name and a patronymic: *How many our Maria Ivanovna will receive, the Russian teachers are interested...* [Russian paper, on September 8, 2019];
2. A nationality → a name: *Our Frits for a long time in Germany. Many Volga region Germans have already received citizenship ...* [Russian paper, on August 16, 2018];
3. Activity → a name: *the Variety Bayan all evening entertained people free-of-charge. Promised money have not paid to starting talent* [Russian paper, on August 30, 2019];
4. A kind of an animal → a name: *It is possible that all troubles which have been comprehended by Murkas', result from their relatives walking on will* [K.T., on January 24, 2017].

4. Conclusion

Onomastic carries represent a special way of interpreting the world around us. Transformations of onyms arise by the natural propensity of the person to compare objects and phenomena; the onomastic metaphor, in particular, arises by the realized or intuitive representation of presence typical in individuals, about reproducibility, another variant of the historical situations, human types, versions of artefacts. Metaphorical carries of onyms reflect installation on program action of a name (the metaphor transfers the attitude to one person, events, or other phenomena to others). Thus, from those mentioned above, it is possible to draw a conclusion that being socially significant and socially fixed speech means onyms-metaphors act as a stimulus of active creative and emotional perception of the text, in this connection are the effective tool of purposeful speech influence in the language of newspapers.

Note on Ethical Issues

The authors confirm that the study does not need ethics committee approval according to the research integrity rules in their country (Date of Confirmation: 12/04/2024).

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